

ISic0284

I.Sicily inscription 0284

Language

Latin

Type

honorific;

building (?)

Material

limestone

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Tauromenium

Place of origin (modern)

Taormina

Provenance

Theatre

Coordinates

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Taormina, Teatro Greco Romano di Taormina

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1

: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2

: mm

Text

Apparatus

Text of CIL

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 491492

EDCS 21900315

Bibliography

Mommsen, Th. 1883. *Inscriptiones Bruttiorum Lucaniae Campaniae Siciliae Sardiniae Latinae. Pars posterior. Inscriptiones Siciliae et Sardiniae. Corpus*

Inscriptionum Latinarum, consilio et auctoritate Academiae Litterarum Regiae Borussicae editum. Berlin. At 10.6996 (<http://arachne.uni-koeln.de/item/buchseite/650752>)

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Manganaro, G. 1988. La Sicilia da Sesto Pompeo a Diocleziano. *ANRW.* 2.11.1: 3-89. At 25 n.101

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Cite as:

J. Prag et al. (2020-12-17): ISic0284. <http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk>. (Collection: TEI edition). <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4334861>